

Economic Growth and Sustainability of China through the Development and Growth of Indigenous Sustainable Brands

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to study the unparalleled economic growth of China focusing especially on the availability of cheap labour, rising GDP per capita and potential labour shortages faced in key sectors. Additionally, the paper will look into the reasons why China should reduce its reliance on producing low margin goods for the Western organisations and develop its own sustainable brands whereby higher levels of margin and thus profit are retained within China. The method selected for the study is qualitative as this is most suitable method given the nature of the topic. Secondary data is used for this purpose and includes resources such as published research papers, journals, online databases, and high-quality reports. The systematic methodology was adopted for this study and secondary data was used. The results show that China will keep dominating the world exports market due to its expansionary policies. Moreover, high growth will keep its balance of payment in surplus and will increase further due to increase in foreign direct investments. Additionally, China should work more on developing economic growth by sustainability through building its own international premium and trusted brands and reduce its tendency to satisfy its domestic markets through copying Western brands.

Keywords: China, Economic Growth, International brands, Expansionary policies, Sustainable brands.

1. INTRODUCTION

The performance of China over the last few decades has been outstanding. This is not only consistent but also higher than the growth of majority of the developed countries of the world [11]. There are several reasons for high economic growth of China:

availability of abundant labour leading to low cost of production, low exchange rate policy leading to high demand for its goods and services, and high saving rate leading to cheap provision of capital for investment. Consistent growth for last 30 years has changed the structure of society and improved the standard of living of many millions of Chinese people. High growth of China has unsettled many developed Western powers and forecasts show that it will continue to dominate the world market in consumer and manufacturing goods [3].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Economic Growth of China

Economic growth is the change in the total goods and services manufactured in the country at any given time. Economic growth is one of the measures for determining the strength of the economy and is a sign of thriving economy [14]. Economic growth of China in last few decades had significantly strengthened the country to the extent that it has become one of the top economies of the world but arguably the most important.

The economic growth of China for the year 2016 was 6.7% and this was lower than the year 2015 when the economic growth was 6.9 percent. For the year 2017, government of China claims to grow by 6.5% although it is the slowest growth in last three decades, it is significant. Similarly, GDP of China for the year 2016 was the highest in since 1978 and it was second highest in the world [1].

In the late 1970s, China started its economic reforms program and was ranked at ninth position having the nominal gross domestic product of around US\$ 214 billion. After 35 years the country was ranked at the second position having the GDP around US\$ 11 trillion in 2015 (Figure 1). Since 1978, China has

shifted from agrarian society to strong manufacturing economy and this could also be said to be the reason for China's engine of growth [10]. The industrialisation helps any economy grow fast as the industries have high growth rates, high saving rate, and high-profit margins. Moreover, within the secondary sector, the highest share of GDP are comprised of industry and construction. As economies grow, they move from primary sector to secondary and then to tertiary sector: the process is called industrialisation and de-industrialisation. When people have increased incomes they demand more services like banking, insurance, tourism, and other leisure-related. This leads to higher proportion of labour force employment in the service sector and higher contribution to GDP. Statistical evidence suggests in 2013, contribution of service sector, secondary sector, and agriculture sector in the GDP are 46.1%, 45.0%, and 8.9%, respectively [5]. The contribution of agricultural in total GDP is falling due to higher demand of workers in the secondary and service sector, however, this is indicative of a rapidly growing economy, increased standards of living and educational standards bring significant benefits to its citizens.

Figure 1. Gross Domestic Goods (US\$)
[16]

2.2 China External Balance Position

The growth of China is an export-led growth and this is the reason that China's balance of payment is enviable. China's current account has been in surplus since 1994 and had experienced deficits only twice. A high surplus in both current account and capital account were mainly due to its high level of exports, which has penetrated the world markets. Moreover, the exports of China are cheaper and in demand throughout the poor and rich countries. The fact that China is capable of producing both the low and high-quality goods and services makes China a major player in international trade world. External Global powers such as the USA & EU have also shown

concern that China is dumping its cheap goods such as steel into the world in order to increase its exports and market share around the world. Thus, China may face growing protectionism as markets may seek to impose tariffs on imports.

China is able to produce goods that satisfy global consumer demand at a highly competitive price. High level of exports brings sufficient foreign reserves into the country and this made the current account reached the highest in the year 2007 when current account was as high as 10.1% of the GDP [5]. China has never reached the same value of current account surplus and the surplus is on a decreasing trend since 2007/08 as shown in figure 2. However, this is due to global slow down including and especially after the 2008 financial crisis. More importantly, China is becoming an attraction for foreign companies as it has the highest population in the world and this is increasing the foreign direct investments (FDI) into the country [3]. Foreign direct investment is now the leading reason that China is experiencing the strong surplus in its capital account of the balance of payments [15]. In the year 2016, the foreign direct investment of China improved to US\$ 118.10 billion, which is an increase of 4.1 percent [5].

Figure 2. Current Account (US\$).
[16]

2.3 Consumer Goods Production and Labour Shortages

China is a large producer of consumer goods owing to its abundance of production facilities. In the year 1990, China produced less than 3% of the world output in manufacturing sector. The global production of China of air-conditioners, mobile phones and shoes are 80%, 70%, and 60%, respectively [5]. These facts show a glimpse that China is producing a larger percentage of consumer goods for global economy. Although China is performing above average, it needs to reconsider its approach towards growth and focus more towards sustainability [12]. There is high potential in the country and numerous companies around the world

have already established their plants and operations in China to take advantage from China's oversupply of labour at cheaper rates. Additionally, China offers an extremely attractive environment for businesses meaning more businesses in the coming years will locate in China, which is positively affecting China's economic growth rate. A recent example being Jaguar Land Rover.

The global slowdown, rising income, and labour shortages are changing the structure of the Chinese economy in many ways. Firstly, the global demand for goods and services are weakening especially in Japan, Europe, and the USA. Nonetheless, the domestic demand is gaining strength, which is compensating the fall in the global demand. The reason is increasing capability of China to produce better quality products that match up to international standards such as technology-related goods, consumer goods, industrial products, and defence goods.

Secondly, the rising GDP per capita, as shown in figure 3, is leading to higher income of people and increasing the standard of living and this has the effect of increasing labour cost of production in China [9]. China is overcoming this issue, as mentioned above, through improving the quantity and quality of goods and services in the country and applying the policy of import-substitution where imported goods are substituted with domestic goods. This would benefit the local industries, increase employment, and GDP [9].

Lastly, it is argued that China is suffering from a labour shortage in key strategic areas such as local global marketing expertise and high-end technology based skills which could change the structure of its trade. The shortage of key skills could prove to be problematic for China with respect to its exports, its balance of payments, and its economic growth. The shortage would drive up the wage rate making Chinese products expensive in the international market [7]. However, China is overcoming this problem with the use of many policies. The increasing and intensive use of technology in all the sectors of the economy would sufficiently compensate the shortage of workforce. In addition, the change with regards to the 'one-child' policy is a long-term plan, which would help China to remain as the dominant country in the world [8]. This would have a number of implications such as a further increase in the labour supply and even more fall in the cost of production, which means China, will keep attracting foreign direct investment into the country and enjoy sustained economic growth [15].

Figure 3. GDP per capita
[16]

2.4 Building Sustainable Brands

It is argued that certain part of the economy in China is transgressing international property right laws and copying the Western brands, ideas, and designs from in the areas like fast-food, architecture, fashion, technology, etc. [2]. The objective is to cater the rising domestic purchasing power of China and to stop domestic people to shifting to foreign premium brands. Although developed countries and international brands criticise China for this approach, every developed country grew the same way when such countries were underdeveloped [6]. As small companies follow established companies, China also initially followed and copied innovative ideas, products, and businesses to keep its economy growing continuously. Every developed economy was once an underdeveloped economy and it grew gradually through applying the economic policies, reforms, and approaches learned from large economies and the same is true for China. In fact, colonial powers such as the British often asset stripped colonies in order to fuel it's own economic growth regardless of the consequences overseas.

The global demand is falling and is affecting the total exports of China; hence it needs to substitute its demand for imported goods with domestic demand in order to keep its pace of high economic growth. China needs to reconsider this approach, as it will not be able to continue with its current economic success for the long term. There are many sustainable ways that China should adopt: it could buy established international brand such as the purchase of Volvo by Geely or it could build global level Chinese brand. These actions will continuously bring money into China without having to depend on exports to fuel economic growth [13].

Furthermore, China needs to focus on keeping a good balance between value additions to its products and lowering cost as rising labour cost. Furthermore, the income generated from the goods and services,

through value addition, would benefit the economic strength of China. This would further have repercussions like lower import bill, positive balance of payments, and strong exchange rate.

3. METHODOLOGY

A systematic review methodology was adopted for this paper as this was the most appropriate method. The systematic methodology makes use of research literature already available and analyses critically what it has to say on the topic we have chosen. The benefits of systematic analysis are, it is a strong form of the methodology chosen for research purpose and there are international standards set for this analysis, which makes it easier for comparison purposes. Moreover, the researcher becomes aware of the previous work done on the subject and this helps him to identify his contribution on the subject.

Secondary data is used in this paper and public defines it as one that is already available and is easily accessible. The benefits of using secondary research are it is readily and cheaply available, however, market intelligence reports are the most detailed form available in the secondary research. This study also used the research undertaken by other researchers and this forms an important part of this paper. Given the nature of the topic, qualitative method is used and quantitative method is rarely used and is limited only to facts taken from published reports and research papers. Qualitative data gives descriptive analysis, point of view, quality reports and insights into the behaviour of people.

The literature consisted of reports and data collected mainly from online libraries and databases. These were World Bank database, International Monetary Funds (IMF) reports, Trading Economics, etc. While accessing the websites many other online sources were accessed which contain large data that was relevant and applicable for this study. Moreover, the data studied was for the last 30 years as this was the time when China started its economic reforms. At the time of studying reports, the authenticity and validity of reports and data were checked so that any predisposition could be removed.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Economic Growth

China is experiencing high economic growth and although the rate has fallen, it is still one of the highest in the world [14]. Many types of research claim that rate of economic growth will slow down,

but the rising domestic aggregate demand is beginning to show positive signs, which will compensate the falling economic growth. Additionally, the manufacturing sector is booming and China is becoming the power hub of established international companies, which will lead to further utilisation of its resources and higher efficiency. Hence, it can be concluded that the changing structure of society will automatically lead the Chinese economy to respond accordingly [14].

4.2 External Balance

The export-led economic growth of China has significantly improved its position of balance of payment and this has led to many benefits. For example, it increases inflows into the country, improves the income and wealth distribution, increases the foreign reserves, enhances the standard of living, and increases the productive capacity of country due to investment in the capital goods [3]. The global slowdown is causing the fall in exports and current account surplus, but increase of foreign direct investment, 4.1% in 2016, into the country has compensated the fall and improved the overall balance of payment position [5]. Furthermore, China has introduced fiscal stimulus into the economy, which will positively affect the society in many ways such as achieving its targets of economic growth for the year 2017. Some Western economists and political leaders have also argued China will find it difficult to achieve its current economic growth China in the long term. However, Chinese authorities hope for continued positive results and aggressive economic reforms aimed at penetrating the world market [3].

4.3 Global Slowdown, Consumer Goods Production and Labour Shortages

The literature review indicates that China plays a major part in the world exports of consumer goods, but there are few issues of concern causing. The global economy fell sharply after the 2007/08 financial crisis and this is causing a slowdown of Chinese economy [4]. Secondly, high economic growth for last 30 years has significantly increased the GDP per capita of China and this is causing local people to prefer more imported goods. Secondly, the rise in aggregate demand for Chinese goods surprisingly causing the shortage of labour force within China and pushing the labour cost upwards. However, China has adopted appropriate policy measures to overcome these issues such as intensive use of technology, changes with regards to the 'one

child' policy, and using boosting domestic aggregate demand [12].

4.4 Building Sustainable Brands

The literature shows that China is not building its own brands and is rigidly following the ideas and strategies of international brands like McDonald's, Apple, Pizza Hut, etc. This is not surprising as every economy followed the same approach when they were in the stage of development. China has adopted this approach so that it could use its resources efficiently and expand into international markets at the same time. Although this is not unsuitable approach, China needs to reconsider its policy in order to achieve long-term sustainability and growth in sectors that offer higher profit margins for local producers. This section concludes that China can adopt sustainability through buying out already established international level brands, targeting niche markets, adding value to its products instead of reducing costs, and building its own international brand [2].

5. CONCLUSION

The paper has looked into the pattern of economic growth of China and its reasons for such high growth are abundant supply of labour in China, which has led to reduction in cost of production. China also has one of the highest saving rates in world which touching 25.945 percent, gross savings and large household saving helps the availability of capital at cheaper rate leading to high investment. A low exchange rate has been a major contributory factor in China's export-led growth as low exchange rate leads to higher demand for exports, generating income and increasing aggregate demand. As a result, China is and will become increasing a global driving force outstripping the USA both in influence and economic might in the near future as many Western nations are saddled with stagnating economies, eye-watering levels of debt both nationally and at a personal level. Thus making China both an attractive and logical base for business both domestic and international.

We conclude based on our study and literature review that the economy of China will keep progressing becoming stronger, more dynamic and flexible and this will achieve macroeconomic objectives like low unemployment, stable inflation, favourable balance of payments, and desirable exchange rate. Furthermore, weak recovery of global economy is restricting China's growth as its growth is highly dependent on exports of consumer's goods.

We also concluded that China needs to reduce its reliance on producing low margin goods and services for Western corporations and should consider adopting a long-term and sustainable strategy through buying out already established international quality and premium brands, targeting profitable niche markets. Thus, develop Chinese-owned brands that are desirable and aspirational for both domestic and global consumption.

6. REFERENCES

- [1]. Backaler, J. (2016). China Goes West: Everything you need to know about Chinese companies going global. Springer.
- [2]. Brisbin, C. (2015). Lost in Translation: A Critique of Copyright and the Aesthetics of Reproduction in China. *Law, Culture and the Humanities*, 1743872115615737.
- [3]. Cai, F., & Lu, Y. (2013). Population change and resulting slowdown in potential GDP growth in China. *China & World Economy*, 21(2), 1-14.
- [4]. Chang, H. J. (2015). The failure of neoliberalism and the future of capitalism. In *Beyond Global Capitalism* (pp. 19-34). Springer Japan.
- [5]. Data.worldbank.org. (2017). China Data. [online] Available at: <http://data.worldbank.org/country/china> [Accessed 22 May 2017].
- [6]. Ding, X., & Li, J. (2015). Incentives for Innovation in China: building an innovative economy (Vol. 124). Routledge.
- [7]. Elfstrom, M., & Kuruvilla, S. (2014). The changing nature of labour unrest in China. *ILR Review*, 67(2), 453-480.
- [8]. Hesketh, T., Zhou, X., & Wang, Y. (2015). The end of the one-child policy: lasting implications for China. *Jama*, 314(24), 2619-2620.
- [9]. Lee, K. C. (2014). Is per capita real GDP stationary in China? Sequential panel selection method. *Economic Modelling*, 37, 507-517.
- [10]. Lin, J. Y. (2013). Demystifying the Chinese economy. *Australian Economic Review*, 46(3), 259-268.
- [11]. Liu, Y., Miletkov, M. K., Wei, Z., & Yang, T. (2015). Board independence and firm performance in China. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 30, 223-244.

- [12]. Popescu, G. H., & Bitoiu, T. I. (2016). Sustainability Strategies of China's Economic Growth Model. *Journal of Self-Governance and Management Economics*, 4(2), 90-96.
- [13]. Ruane, C. (2017). Fan Yang. Faked in China: Nation Branding, Counterfeit Culture, and Globalization.
- [14]. Tang, B. (2015). Real exchange rate and economic growth in China: A cointegrated VAR approach. *China Economic Review*, 34, 293-310.
- [15]. Zhang, K. H. (2014). How does foreign direct investment affect industrial competitiveness? Evidence from China. *China economic review*, 30, 530-539.
- [16]. Trading Economics, "*China – Economic Indicators*", retrieved from <https://tradingeconomics.com/china/indicators>